

Cambridge Centre for Proteomics Mascot Search Results

User : anja
Email : aa2030@cam.ac.uk
Search title : P378 (\\prot-filesvr1\data\CORE\PARAMETERS\Mascot_search_parameters\Yagnesh\M291_Ben_Luisi_tolc_arca_velos_xlink_ox_chymo_041218.par), submitted from Daemon on CCP-PC158
MS data file : \\prot-filesvr1\data\CORE\RAW_DATA_2018_Velos\P378_Ben_Luisi\P378_Band_5.mgf
Database 1 : cRAP 20181217 (120 sequences; 39582 residues)
Database 2 : M291_ARCA ARCA 20181203 (1 sequences; 238 residues)
Database 3 : M291_TOLC TOLC_20181203 (1 sequences; 493 residues)
Timestamp : 19 Dec 2018 at 10:00:05 GMT

Protein hits : [1::sp|cRAP087|P02769|ALBU BOVIN](#) Serum albumin OS=Bos taurus GN=ALB PE=1
[1::sp|cRAP022|P00766|CTRA BOVIN](#) Chymotrypsinogen A OS=Bos taurus PE=1 S
[3::sp|P02930|TOLC ECOLI](#) Outer membrane protein TolC OS=Escheric
[1::sp|cRAP008|P00722|BGAL ECOLI](#) Beta-galactosidase OS=Escherichia coli
[1::sp|cRAP002|P02768|ALBU HUMAN](#) Serum albumin OS=Homo sapiens GN=ALB PE
[1::sp|cRAP112|P00761|TRYP PIG](#) Trypsin OS=Sus scrofa PE=1 SV=1
[1::sp|cRAP030|P32503|GAG SCVLA](#) Major capsid protein OS=Saccharomyces c
[1::sp|cRAP115|P63279|UBC9 HUMAN](#) SUMO-conjugating enzyme UBC9 OS=Homo sa
[1::sp|cRAP034|P09211|GSTP1 HUMAN](#) Glutathione S-transferase P OS=Homo sap
[1::sp|cRAP015|P02666|CASB BOVIN](#) Beta-casein OS=Bos taurus GN=CSN2 PE=1
[1::sp|cRAP020|P01031|CO5 HUMAN](#) Complement C5 OS=Homo sapiens GN=C5 PE=
[1::sp|cRAP089|P00792|PEPA BOVIN](#) Pepsin A OS=Bos taurus GN=PGA PE=1 SV=2
[1::sp|cRAP104|P12081|SYHC HUMAN](#) Histidine--tRNA ligase, cytoplasmic OS=
[1::sp|cRAP054|P04264|K2C1 HUMAN](#) Keratin, type II cytoskeletal 1 OS=Homo
[1::sp|cRAP004|P04745|AMY1 HUMAN](#) Alpha-amylase 1 OS=Homo sapiens GN=AMY1
[1::sp|cRAP084|P15559|NQO1 HUMAN](#) NAD(P)H dehydrogenase [quinone] 1 OS=Ho
[1::sp|cRAP077|P41159|LEP HUMAN](#) Leptin OS=Homo sapiens GN=LEP PE=1 SV=1
[1::sp|cRAP086|P01012|OVAL CHICK](#) Ovalbumin OS=Gallus gallus GN=SERPINB14
[1::sp|cRAP114|O00762|UBE2C HUMAN](#) Ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme E2 C OS=Ho

Mascot Score Histogram

Ions score is $-10 \cdot \log(P)$, where P is the probability that the observed match is a random event. Individual ions scores > 15 indicate identity or extensive homology ($p < 0.05$). Protein scores are derived from ions scores as a non-probabilistic basis for ranking protein hits.

Peptide Summary Report

Protein Family Summary	Peptide Summary	Select Summary (protein hits)	Select Summary (unassigned)	Exp
Significance threshold p<				
Standard scoring MudPIT scoring				
Show pop-ups Suppress pop-ups				
Preferred taxonomy All entries .. Archaea (Archaeobacteria) .. Eukaryota (eucaryotes) Alveolata (alveolates and relatives) bony vertebrates lobe-finned fish and tetrapod clade Mammalia (mammals) Mus musculus (house mouse) Rattus norvegicus (brown rat) Other Mammals (mammals) fishes) Takifugu rubripes (Japanese Pufferfish) Danio rerio (zebra fish) Schizosaccharomyces pombe (fission yeast) Pneumocystis carinii Other Fungi Viridiplantae (green plants) Mycobacterium tuberculosis complex Other Actinobacteria (class) Firmicutes (gram-positive bacteria) Agrobacterium tumefaciens Campylobacter jejuni Escherichia coli Neisseria meningitidis (meningococcus) Species information unavailable				

Error tolerant

- [1::sp|cRAP087|P02769|ALBU BOVIN](#) **Mass:** 71244 **Score:** 1352 **Matches:** 154 (154) S
 Serum albumin OS=Bos taurus GN=ALB PE=1 SV=4
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
300	392.7144	783.4142	783.4127	2.00	0	20	0.0099	1	U	L.KPD
399	396.6891	791.3636	791.3636	-0.06	1	(20)	0.0092	1		Y.LQQ
400	396.6891	791.3637	791.3636	0.09	1	23	0.0046	1		Y.LQQ
888	415.2610	828.5075	828.5069	0.75	2	22	0.0056	1	U	L.SLI
1154	426.2107	850.4068	850.4072	-0.56	1	(23)	0.0059	1	U	L.VNE
1155	426.2108	850.4070	850.4072	-0.28	1	36	0.00027	1	U	L.VNE
1157	426.2111	850.4076	850.4072	0.38	1	(35)	0.00035	1	U	L.VNE

<u>1347</u>	434.7153	867.4161	867.4160	0.09	0	34	0.00042	1	U	L.KTV
<u>1348</u>	434.7159	867.4173	867.4160	1.50	0	(33)	0.00045	1	U	L.KTV
<u>1795</u>	457.2243	912.4341	912.4341	-0.01	1	(27)	0.0025	1	U	Y.ANK
<u>1796</u>	457.2244	912.4342	912.4341	0.15	1	31	0.00091	1	U	Y.ANK
<u>1904</u>	461.2377	920.4608	920.4603	0.50	1	(21)	0.0074	1	U	Y.QEA
<u>1906</u>	461.2380	920.4613	920.4603	1.11	1	23	0.0047	1	U	Y.QEA
<u>2600</u>	487.7263	973.4380	973.4505	-12.79	1	(24)	0.0041	1	U	F.KDL
<u>2604</u>	487.7319	973.4492	973.4505	-1.29	1	(33)	0.00052	1	U	F.KDL
<u>2605</u>	487.7321	973.4496	973.4505	-0.96	1	(22)	0.0061	1	U	F.KDL
<u>2606</u>	487.7322	973.4498	973.4505	-0.71	1	(33)	0.00052	1	U	F.KDL
<u>2607</u>	487.7322	973.4498	973.4505	-0.71	1	(34)	0.0004	1	U	F.KDL
<u>2608</u>	487.7323	973.4501	973.4505	-0.40	1	(49)	1.4e-05	1	U	F.KDL
<u>2609</u>	487.7323	973.4501	973.4505	-0.40	1	52	6.1e-06	1	U	F.KDL
<u>2610</u>	487.7323	973.4501	973.4505	-0.40	1	(23)	0.0055	1	U	F.KDL
<u>2611</u>	487.7324	973.4502	973.4505	-0.34	1	(31)	0.00078	1	U	F.KDL
<u>2612</u>	487.7324	973.4503	973.4505	-0.16	1	(21)	0.0089	1	U	F.KDL
<u>2613</u>	487.7325	973.4504	973.4505	-0.09	1	(32)	0.00073	1	U	F.KDL
<u>2614</u>	487.7326	973.4507	973.4505	0.23	1	(22)	0.0059	1	U	F.KDL
<u>2615</u>	487.7327	973.4508	973.4505	0.30	1	(49)	1.4e-05	1	U	F.KDL
<u>2616</u>	487.7327	973.4508	973.4505	0.36	1	(28)	0.0017	1	U	F.KDL
<u>2617</u>	487.7329	973.4512	973.4505	0.73	1	(29)	0.0012	1	U	F.KDL
<u>2619</u>	487.7329	973.4513	973.4505	0.79	1	(25)	0.003	1	U	F.KDL
<u>2620</u>	487.7330	973.4514	973.4505	0.91	1	(25)	0.0031	1	U	F.KDL
<u>2621</u>	487.7331	973.4517	973.4505	1.22	1	(31)	0.00087	1	U	F.KDL
<u>2623</u>	487.7332	973.4518	973.4505	1.34	1	(40)	0.00011	1	U	F.KDL
<u>2625</u>	487.7335	973.4524	973.4505	1.92	1	(33)	0.00054	1	U	F.KDL
<u>2915</u>	498.7297	995.4449	995.4447	0.12	1	45	3.1e-05	1	U	F.SAL
<u>2916</u>	498.7301	995.4456	995.4447	0.84	1	(43)	4.6e-05	1	U	F.SAL
<u>3639</u>	525.2418	1048.4691	1048.4681	0.90	0	(26)	0.0025	1	U	L.KEC
<u>3640</u>	525.2425	1048.4704	1048.4681	2.18	0	32	0.00063	1	U	L.KEC
<u>3664</u>	526.2816	1050.5486	1050.5498	-1.18	1	46	2.5e-05	1	U	F.KAD
<u>3665</u>	526.2823	1050.5500	1050.5498	0.21	1	(36)	0.00024	1	U	F.KAD
<u>3667</u>	526.7447	1051.4748	1051.4757	-0.81	0	(21)	0.014	1	U	L.IKQ
<u>3670</u>	526.7458	1051.4770	1051.4757	1.28	0	48	2.7e-05	1	U	L.IKQ
<u>3671</u>	526.7462	1051.4779	1051.4757	2.10	0	(42)	0.00011	1	U	L.IKQ
<u>3681</u>	527.2366	1052.4586	1052.4597	-1.04	0	(35)	0.00048	1	U	L.IKQ
<u>3682</u>	527.2368	1052.4591	1052.4597	-0.57	0	(39)	0.00021	1	U	L.IKQ
<u>3826</u>	532.7194	1063.4242	1063.4240	0.13	0	(33)	0.00053	1		L.ECA
<u>3827</u>	532.7194	1063.4242	1063.4240	0.13	0	(26)	0.0023	1		L.ECA
<u>3828</u>	532.7201	1063.4257	1063.4240	1.62	0	38	0.00015	1		L.ECA
<u>4098</u>	541.2878	1080.5610	1080.5604	0.58	0	38	0.00015	1	U	L.SQK
<u>4099</u>	541.2881	1080.5617	1080.5604	1.27	0	(22)	0.0064	1	U	L.SQK
<u>4100</u>	541.2886	1080.5626	1080.5604	2.04	0	(32)	0.00067	1	U	L.SQK
<u>4110</u>	541.7769	1081.5393	1081.5444	-4.72	0	(30)	0.00091	1	U	L.SQK
<u>5225</u>	589.2618	1176.5090	1176.5081	0.78	1	(37)	0.0002	1		L.LEC
<u>5226</u>	589.2618	1176.5090	1176.5081	0.78	1	41	8.4e-05	1		L.LEC
<u>5267</u>	590.8275	1179.6405	1179.6400	0.37	2	(35)	0.00028	1	U	Y.GFQ
<u>5268</u>	590.8289	1179.6433	1179.6400	2.76	2	42	6e-05	1	U	Y.GFQ
<u>5446</u>	596.8188	1191.6231	1191.6248	-1.36	1	(38)	0.00016	1	U	L.KHL
<u>5447</u>	596.8189	1191.6233	1191.6248	-1.26	1	48	1.5e-05	1	U	L.KHL
<u>5466</u>	597.3115	1192.6085	1192.6088	-0.24	1	(40)	0.00011	1	U	L.KHL
<u>5467</u>	597.3123	1192.6101	1192.6088	1.10	1	(45)	3.3e-05	1	U	L.KHL
<u>5469</u>	398.5569	1192.6489	1192.6492	-0.22	2	(21)	0.0071	1	U	Y.VPK
<u>5471</u>	398.5572	1192.6498	1192.6492	0.53	2	(23)	0.0055	1	U	Y.VPK
<u>5472</u>	398.5573	1192.6502	1192.6492	0.83	2	30	0.0011	1	U	Y.VPK
<u>5892</u>	613.8142	1225.6139	1225.6125	1.13	1	22	0.0068	1	U	L.CKV
<u>6102</u>	621.2696	1240.5246	1240.5394	-11.88	0	(23)	0.0052	1	U	F.AED

<u>6105</u>	414.5203	1240.5391	1240.5394	-0.20	0	(20)	0.011	1	U	F.AED
<u>6106</u>	414.5208	1240.5404	1240.5394	0.84	0	(21)	0.0087	1	U	F.AED
<u>6107</u>	621.2783	1240.5420	1240.5394	2.08	0	37	0.00022	1	U	F.AED
<u>6108</u>	621.2792	1240.5439	1240.5394	3.66	0	(30)	0.001	1	U	F.AED
<u>7015</u>	654.8673	1307.7201	1307.7197	0.27	0	(41)	8.9e-05	1	U	L.KHK
<u>7019</u>	654.8676	1307.7207	1307.7197	0.73	0	(25)	0.0031	1	U	L.KHK
<u>7020</u>	654.8677	1307.7208	1307.7197	0.84	0	(30)	0.00096	1	U	L.KHK
<u>7024</u>	654.8693	1307.7241	1307.7197	3.35	0	41	7.1e-05	1	U	L.KHK
<u>7240</u>	663.8904	1325.7662	1325.7667	-0.38	0	(34)	0.00037	1	U	Y.TRK
<u>7241</u>	663.8917	1325.7688	1325.7667	1.55	0	41	8.3e-05	1	U	Y.TRK
<u>7486</u>	451.2334	1350.6784	1350.6779	0.33	0	36	0.00033	1	U	L.SHK
<u>7487</u>	451.2335	1350.6786	1350.6779	0.46	0	(35)	0.00036	1	U	L.SHK
<u>7876</u>	697.3342	1392.6539	1392.6555	-1.13	0	(25)	0.0038	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7877</u>	697.3344	1392.6543	1392.6555	-0.88	0	(50)	1.3e-05	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7878</u>	697.3346	1392.6546	1392.6555	-0.62	0	(33)	0.00057	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7879</u>	697.3350	1392.6554	1392.6555	-0.09	0	(37)	0.00022	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7880</u>	697.3350	1392.6554	1392.6555	-0.09	0	(45)	3.7e-05	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7881</u>	697.3353	1392.6561	1392.6555	0.45	0	(55)	3.9e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7882</u>	697.3357	1392.6568	1392.6555	0.96	0	(37)	0.00022	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7883</u>	697.3357	1392.6568	1392.6555	0.96	0	(59)	1.5e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7884</u>	697.3358	1392.6571	1392.6555	1.15	0	(66)	3.1e-07	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7885</u>	697.3359	1392.6572	1392.6555	1.24	0	(33)	0.00058	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7886</u>	697.3360	1392.6574	1392.6555	1.41	0	(68)	2.1e-07	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7887</u>	697.3361	1392.6577	1392.6555	1.58	0	(25)	0.0035	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7888</u>	697.3362	1392.6578	1392.6555	1.67	0	(56)	2.8e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7889</u>	697.3363	1392.6580	1392.6555	1.84	0	(49)	1.2e-05	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7890</u>	697.3364	1392.6583	1392.6555	2.03	0	(53)	5.1e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7891</u>	697.3365	1392.6584	1392.6555	2.11	0	(31)	0.00086	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7892</u>	697.3366	1392.6587	1392.6555	2.28	0	(48)	1.6e-05	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7893</u>	697.3367	1392.6588	1392.6555	2.37	0	(70)	1.1e-07	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7894</u>	697.3367	1392.6588	1392.6555	2.37	0	(60)	1e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7895</u>	697.3368	1392.6590	1392.6555	2.54	0	(71)	8.4e-08	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7896</u>	697.3369	1392.6591	1392.6555	2.63	0	(46)	2.6e-05	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7897</u>	697.3369	1392.6593	1392.6555	2.71	0	(40)	0.00011	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7898</u>	697.3370	1392.6594	1392.6555	2.82	0	(53)	5.4e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7899</u>	697.3371	1392.6596	1392.6555	2.99	0	(43)	5e-05	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7900</u>	697.3372	1392.6599	1392.6555	3.16	0	(22)	0.0061	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7901</u>	697.3372	1392.6599	1392.6555	3.16	0	(64)	4e-07	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7902</u>	697.3373	1392.6600	1392.6555	3.25	0	(57)	2.2e-06	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7903</u>	697.3373	1392.6600	1392.6555	3.25	0	(50)	1.1e-05	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7904</u>	697.3375	1392.6604	1392.6555	3.50	0	(60)	9.6e-07	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7905</u>	697.3377	1392.6609	1392.6555	3.86	0	(40)	9.7e-05	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7917</u>	697.8267	1393.6389	1393.6395	-0.44	0	72	1.2e-07	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>7918</u>	697.8386	1393.6627	1393.6395	16.6	0	(21)	0.013	1	U	Y.ICD
<u>8142</u>	711.4101	1420.8056	1420.8038	1.32	1	(27)	0.0021	1	U	L.LKH
<u>8143</u>	711.4114	1420.8082	1420.8038	3.12	1	31	0.00083	1	U	L.LKH
<u>9210</u>	784.8124	1567.6102	1567.6065	2.36	0	(31)	0.00073	1	U	F.QEC
<u>9211</u>	784.8126	1567.6106	1567.6065	2.59	0	(27)	0.002	1	U	F.QEC
<u>9212</u>	784.8128	1567.6111	1567.6065	2.91	0	(38)	0.00017	1	U	F.QEC
<u>9213</u>	784.8144	1567.6142	1567.6065	4.93	0	(31)	0.00087	1	U	F.QEC
<u>9229</u>	785.3032	1568.5919	1568.5905	0.88	0	(40)	9.4e-05	1	U	F.QEC
<u>9230</u>	785.3054	1568.5963	1568.5905	3.68	0	44	4e-05	1	U	F.QEC
<u>9267</u>	787.3892	1572.7638	1572.7671	-2.14	2	(39)	0.00013	1	U	F.DEH
<u>9269</u>	787.3913	1572.7680	1572.7671	0.58	2	46	2.5e-05	1	U	F.DEH
<u>9328</u>	792.4545	1582.8945	1582.8930	0.94	2	(21)	0.0074	1	U	F.AVE
<u>9335</u>	792.9462	1583.8778	1583.8770	0.48	2	23	0.005	1	U	F.AVE
<u>9336</u>	792.9481	1583.8816	1583.8770	2.87	2	(22)	0.0066	1	U	F.AVE

9705	827.8019	1653.5892	1653.5858	2.08	0	38	0.00015	1	U	L.EEC
9707	827.8025	1653.5904	1653.5858	2.82	0	(27)	0.0018	1	U	L.EEC
9912	844.8381	1687.6616	1687.6640	-1.45	0	(29)	0.0012	1	U	F.VDK
9913	563.5617	1687.6633	1687.6640	-0.43	0	(28)	0.0016	1	U	F.VDK
9914	844.8394	1687.6643	1687.6640	0.15	0	(41)	8.1e-05	1	U	F.VDK
9916	844.8400	1687.6654	1687.6640	0.80	0	(61)	8.2e-07	1	U	F.VDK
9919	844.8417	1687.6688	1687.6640	2.82	0	62	6.2e-07	1	U	F.VDK
9920	844.8445	1687.6744	1687.6640	6.15	0	(38)	0.00021	1	U	F.VDK
10325	591.2817	1770.8234	1770.8247	-0.72	2	29	0.0022	1	U	L.IKQ
11147	1034.9087	2067.8028	2067.7972	2.72	1	52	5.9e-06	1	U	Y.EAT
11148	690.2750	2067.8031	2067.7972	2.82	1	(28)	0.0015	1	U	Y.EAT
11150	1034.9093	2067.8040	2067.7972	3.31	1	(51)	7.8e-06	1	U	Y.EAT
11271	530.0267	2116.0778	2116.0800	-1.05	1	(23)	0.0052	1	U	L.SHK
11272	706.3679	2116.0819	2116.0800	0.90	1	(33)	0.00061	1	U	L.SHK
11273	1059.0488	2116.0831	2116.0800	1.45	1	53	6.4e-06	1	U	L.SHK
11274	530.0281	2116.0835	2116.0800	1.62	1	(27)	0.0022	1	U	L.SHK
11275	706.3689	2116.0849	2116.0800	2.29	1	(35)	0.0004	1	U	L.SHK
11276	530.0286	2116.0851	2116.0800	2.41	1	(28)	0.0019	1	U	L.SHK
11279	1059.0516	2116.0887	2116.0800	4.11	1	(44)	3.9e-05	1	U	L.SHK
11404	744.0605	2229.1596	2229.1641	-2.00	2	(35)	0.00029	1	U	F.LSH
11406	1115.5895	2229.1644	2229.1641	0.14	2	(32)	0.00062	1	U	F.LSH
11408	744.0624	2229.1653	2229.1641	0.55	2	37	0.00019	1	U	F.LSH
11410	558.2993	2229.1679	2229.1641	1.72	2	(23)	0.0052	1	U	F.LSH
11412	558.2996	2229.1691	2229.1641	2.26	2	(21)	0.0074	1	U	F.LSH
11413	1115.5930	2229.1715	2229.1641	3.32	2	(29)	0.0014	1	U	F.LSH
11472	758.9560	2273.8461	2273.8446	0.69	0	(35)	0.00029	1	U	Y.GDM
11473	1137.9316	2273.8487	2273.8446	1.83	0	48	1.4e-05	1	U	Y.GDM
11474	1137.9341	2273.8536	2273.8446	3.97	0	(37)	0.00018	1	U	Y.GDM
11475	758.9586	2273.8539	2273.8446	4.08	0	(47)	2.1e-05	1	U	Y.GDM
11476	759.2891	2274.8454	2274.8286	7.37	0	(33)	0.00056	1	U	Y.GDM
11492	764.2882	2289.8428	2289.8395	1.45	0	(40)	0.00011	1	U	Y.GDM
11493	1145.9294	2289.8443	2289.8395	2.11	0	(27)	0.0018	1	U	Y.GDM
11494	764.2891	2289.8454	2289.8395	2.56	0	(31)	0.0008	1	U	Y.GDM

2. [1::sp|cRAP022|P00766|CTRA_BOVIN](#) Mass: 26220 Score: 248 Matches: 16(16) Seq

Chymotrypsinogen A OS=Bos taurus PE=1 SV=1

Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
838	412.7290	823.4434	823.4440	-0.61	1	(35)	0.00032	1	U	L.KLSTA
840	412.7292	823.4439	823.4440	-0.01	1	55	3e-06	1	U	L.KLSTA
1430	437.7557	873.4968	873.4960	0.91	1	23	0.005	1	U	W.TLVGI
1431	437.7557	873.4969	873.4960	0.97	1	(23)	0.0055	1	U	W.TLVGI
2995	501.2541	1000.4936	1000.4938	-0.19	0	(26)	0.0027	1	U	Y.TNANT
2996	501.2541	1000.4937	1000.4938	-0.07	0	(25)	0.0034	1	U	Y.TNANT
3001	501.7442	1001.4738	1001.4778	-3.91	0	(26)	0.0025	1	U	Y.TNANT
3023	502.2356	1002.4567	1002.4618	-5.06	0	32	0.00068	1	U	Y.TNANT
3024	502.2357	1002.4568	1002.4618	-4.94	0	(30)	0.0011	1	U	Y.TNANT
3195	508.7852	1015.5559	1015.5550	0.91	1	56	2.4e-06	1	U	L.TINND
3196	508.7853	1015.5561	1015.5550	1.09	1	(50)	9.8e-06	1	U	L.TINND
3197	508.7860	1015.5574	1015.5550	2.41	1	(28)	0.0015	1	U	L.TINND
4559	561.7928	1121.5710	1121.5717	-0.60	1	22	0.0069	1	U	W.QVSLQ

10216	869.9562	1737.8978	1737.9009	-1.80	1	39	0.00012	1	U	Y.TNANT
10217	869.9585	1737.9024	1737.9009	0.87	1	(35)	0.0003	1	U	Y.TNANT
10362	892.4424	1782.8703	1782.8689	0.79	0	21	0.018	1	U	L.SRIVN

3. [3::sp|P02930|TOLC ECOLI](#) Mass: 53708 Score: 229 Matches: 11(11) Sequences:
 Outer membrane protein TolC OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) OX=83333 GN=tolC PE=1 SV=2
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1162	426.2224	850.4302	850.4297	0.59	0	23	0.0047	1	U	L.RQITG
1163	426.2226	850.4307	850.4297	1.18	0	(22)	0.0061	1	U	L.RQITG
2466	482.7404	963.4663	963.4662	0.14	1	(31)	0.00094	1	U	Y.NFVGA
2467	482.7406	963.4666	963.4662	0.51	1	38	0.00016	1	U	Y.NFVGA
3010	501.7584	1001.5023	1001.5029	-0.58	2	35	0.00031	1	U	L.GTLNE
3604	523.7797	1045.5448	1045.5444	0.35	2	37	0.00018	1	U	L.LPQLG
3605	523.7800	1045.5454	1045.5444	0.94	2	(33)	0.00046	1	U	L.LPQLG
9452	804.9210	1607.8274	1607.8307	-2.08	2	34	0.00049	1	U	L.RQITG
9453	804.9223	1607.8300	1607.8307	-0.42	2	(23)	0.0061	1	U	L.RQITG
10698	936.4583	1870.9019	1870.9020	-0.05	1	63	1.4e-06	1	U	L.ANEVT
10699	936.4597	1870.9049	1870.9020	1.52	1	(47)	6.2e-05	1	U	L.ANEVT

4. [1::sp|cRAP008|P00722|BGAL ECOLI](#) Mass: 117321 Score: 197 Matches: 9(9) Sequences:
 Beta-galactosidase OS=Escherichia coli (strain K12) GN=lacZ PE=1 SV=2
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
2292	477.2182	952.4218	952.4212	0.71	1	27	0.0022	1	U	W.DLPLS
3964	536.7924	1071.5703	1071.5461	22.5	0	24	0.0039	1	U	L.AQVAE
4113	541.8135	1081.6124	1081.6131	-0.68	1	(31)	0.00086	1	U	W.LSLPG
4116	541.8146	1081.6147	1081.6131	1.46	1	38	0.00014	1	U	W.LSLPG
8576	736.3809	1470.7472	1470.7467	0.34	2	(48)	1.6e-05	1	U	W.LGLGP
8577	736.3816	1470.7486	1470.7467	1.33	2	80	1.1e-08	1	U	W.LGLGP
8594	736.8750	1471.7354	1471.7307	3.24	2	(26)	0.0027	1	U	W.LGLGP
8689	741.8747	1481.7348	1481.7362	-0.91	1	33	0.00049	1	U	F.RLSGQ
8690	741.8773	1481.7401	1481.7362	2.64	1	(32)	0.00066	1	U	F.RLSGQ

5. [1::sp|cRAP002|P02768|ALBU HUMAN](#) Mass: 71317 Score: 163 Matches: 32(32) Sequences:
 Serum albumin OS=Homo sapiens GN=ALB PE=1 SV=2
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
204	387.2238	772.4330	772.4331	-0.04	1	20	0.0095	1	U	L.SVVLN
399	396.6891	791.3636	791.3636	-0.06	1	(20)	0.0092	1		Y.LQQCP
400	396.6891	791.3637	791.3636	0.09	1	23	0.0046	1		Y.LQQCP
3826	532.7194	1063.4242	1063.4240	0.13	0	(33)	0.00053	1		L.ECADD
3827	532.7194	1063.4242	1063.4240	0.13	0	(26)	0.0023	1		L.ECADD
3828	532.7201	1063.4257	1063.4240	1.62	0	38	0.00015	1		L.ECADD
5225	589.2618	1176.5090	1176.5081	0.78	1	(37)	0.0002	1		L.LECAD
5226	589.2618	1176.5090	1176.5081	0.78	1	41	8.4e-05	1		L.LECAD

7876	697.3342	1392.6539	1392.6555	-1.12	0	(21)	0.0086	2	U	Y.ICENQ
7877	697.3344	1392.6543	1392.6555	-0.86	0	(27)	0.0026	2	U	Y.ICENQ
7879	697.3350	1392.6554	1392.6555	-0.07	0	(27)	0.0027	2	U	Y.ICENQ
7880	697.3350	1392.6554	1392.6555	-0.07	0	(22)	0.0082	2	U	Y.ICENQ
7881	697.3353	1392.6561	1392.6555	0.46	0	(24)	0.0054	2	U	Y.ICENQ
7882	697.3357	1392.6568	1392.6555	0.97	0	(23)	0.0054	2	U	Y.ICENQ
7883	697.3357	1392.6568	1392.6555	0.97	0	(22)	0.007	2	U	Y.ICENQ
7884	697.3358	1392.6571	1392.6555	1.16	0	(36)	0.00033	2	U	Y.ICENQ
7886	697.3360	1392.6574	1392.6555	1.42	0	(29)	0.0014	2	U	Y.ICENQ
7888	697.3362	1392.6578	1392.6555	1.68	0	(28)	0.0021	2	U	Y.ICENQ
7889	697.3363	1392.6580	1392.6555	1.85	0	(27)	0.0023	2	U	Y.ICENQ
7890	697.3364	1392.6583	1392.6555	2.04	0	(23)	0.0049	2	U	Y.ICENQ
7892	697.3366	1392.6587	1392.6555	2.29	0	(23)	0.0049	2	U	Y.ICENQ
7893	697.3367	1392.6588	1392.6555	2.38	0	(27)	0.0021	2	U	Y.ICENQ
7894	697.3367	1392.6588	1392.6555	2.38	0	(25)	0.0032	2	U	Y.ICENQ
7895	697.3368	1392.6590	1392.6555	2.55	0	40	0.0001	2	U	Y.ICENQ
7897	697.3369	1392.6593	1392.6555	2.73	0	(21)	0.009	2	U	Y.ICENQ
7898	697.3370	1392.6594	1392.6555	2.83	0	(21)	0.008	2	U	Y.ICENQ
7901	697.3372	1392.6599	1392.6555	3.17	0	(32)	0.00062	2	U	Y.ICENQ
7902	697.3373	1392.6600	1392.6555	3.26	0	(24)	0.0041	2	U	Y.ICENQ
7903	697.3373	1392.6600	1392.6555	3.26	0	(20)	0.01	2	U	Y.ICENQ
7904	697.3375	1392.6604	1392.6555	3.52	0	(25)	0.0031	2	U	Y.ICENQ
7905	697.3377	1392.6609	1392.6555	3.87	0	(21)	0.0091	2	U	Y.ICENQ
7917	697.8267	1393.6389	1393.6395	-0.43	0	(33)	0.00089	3	U	Y.ICENQ

6. [1::sp|cRAP112|P00761|TRYP_PIG](#) Mass: 25078 Score: 81 Matches: 4(4) Sequenc
 Trypsin OS=Sus scrofa PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
4004	538.2632	1074.5118	1074.5094	2.21	1	36	0.00035	1	U	Y.QVSLN
4023	538.7634	1075.5123	1075.4934	17.5	1	(22)	0.0074	1	U	Y.QVSLN
6355	629.3325	1256.6505	1256.6513	-0.66	1	46	2.8e-05	1	U	Y.VNWIQ
6356	629.3331	1256.6516	1256.6513	0.21	1	(35)	0.00031	1	U	Y.VNWIQ

7. [1::sp|cRAP030|P32503|GAG_SCVLA](#) Mass: 76402 Score: 48 Matches: 2(2) Sequen
 Major capsid protein OS=Saccharomyces cerevisiae virus L-A GN=gag PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
17	380.2215	758.4284	758.4174	14.5	2	48	1.6e-05	1	U	F.LLSGDA
19	380.2217	758.4288	758.4174	15.0	2	(35)	0.0003	1	U	F.LLSGDA

8. [1::sp|cRAP115|P63279|UBC9_HUMAN](#) Mass: 18223 Score: 31 Matches: 2(2) Sequen
 SUMO-conjugating enzyme UBC9 OS=Homo sapiens GN=UBE2I PE=1 SV=1
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
10206	579.3157	1734.9252	1734.9199	3.06	1	31	0.0011	1	U	Y.EKRVRA
10207	579.3174	1734.9305	1734.9199	6.12	1	(27)	0.0025	1	U	Y.EKRVRA

9. [1::sp|cRAP034|P09211|GSTP1 HUMAN](#) Mass: 23569 Score: 27 Matches: 2(2) Sequen
 Glutathione S-transferase P OS=Homo sapiens GN=GSTP1 PE=1 SV=2
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
3689	527.2702	1052.5258	1052.5390	-12.47	2	27	0.0021	1	U	L.TLYQS
3690	527.2707	1052.5268	1052.5390	-11.54	2	(22)	0.0065	1	U	L.TLYQS

10. [1::sp|cRAP015|P02666|CASB BOVIN](#) Mass: 25148 Score: 24 Matches: 4(4) Sequen
 Beta-casein OS=Bos taurus GN=CSN2 PE=1 SV=2
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1177	426.7289	851.4432	851.4496	-7.54	1	(23)	0.0048	1	U	-.MKVLIL.A
1178	426.7289	851.4433	851.4496	-7.47	1	(20)	0.0097	1	U	-.MKVLIL.A
1179	426.7290	851.4435	851.4496	-7.19	1	27	0.0021	1	U	-.MKVLIL.A
1180	426.7293	851.4441	851.4496	-6.46	1	(24)	0.0037	1	U	-.MKVLIL.A

11. [1::sp|cRAP020|P01031|CO5 HUMAN](#) Mass: 189897 Score: 23 Matches: 1(1) Sequen
 Complement C5 OS=Homo sapiens GN=C5 PE=1 SV=4
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
10350	890.9603	1779.9061	1779.9189	-7.20	1	23	0.0064	1	U	Y.SVVRGE

12. [1::sp|cRAP089|P00792|PEPA BOVIN](#) Mass: 40320 Score: 22 Matches: 1(1) Sequen
 Pepsin A OS=Bos taurus GN=PGA PE=1 SV=2
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
206	387.2243	772.4340	772.4443	-13.24	0	22	0.0059	1	U	Y.IREAATL

13. [1::sp|cRAP104|P12081|SYHC HUMAN](#) Mass: 57944 Score: 22 Matches: 2(2) Sequen
 Histidine--tRNA ligase, cytoplasmic OS=Homo sapiens GN=HARS PE=1 SV=2
 Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr (expt)	Mr (calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
4905	575.7841	1149.5536	1149.5773	-20.67	1	(21)	0.0076	1	U	L.VASAO
4907	575.7863	1149.5581	1149.5773	-16.74	1	22	0.0062	1	U	L.VASAO

14. [1::sp|cRAP054|P04264|K2C1 HUMAN](#) Mass: 66170 Score: 22 Matches: 1(1) Sequen
Keratin, type II cytoskeletal 1 OS=Homo sapiens GN=KRT1 PE=1 SV=6
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr(expt)	Mr(calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
415	397.6985	793.3824	793.3714	13.8	0	22	0.0067	1	U	Y.MTKVDL.Q

15. [1::sp|cRAP004|P04745|AMY1 HUMAN](#) Mass: 58415 Score: 22 Matches: 2(2) Sequen
Alpha-amylase 1 OS=Homo sapiens GN=AMY1A PE=1 SV=2
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr(expt)	Mr(calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1490	440.2264	878.4381	878.4246	15.4	0	(21)	0.0074	1	U	F.GNGRVTEF
1491	440.2269	878.4392	878.4246	16.6	0	22	0.007	1	U	F.GNGRVTEF

16. [1::sp|cRAP084|P15559|NQO1 HUMAN](#) Mass: 30905 Score: 21 Matches: 1(1) Sequen
NAD(P)H dehydrogenase [quinone] 1 OS=Homo sapiens GN=NQO1 PE=1 SV=1
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr(expt)	Mr(calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
541	401.7374	801.4602	801.4643	-5.14	0	21	0.0072	1	U	-.MVGRRAL.

17. [1::sp|cRAP077|P41159|LEP HUMAN](#) Mass: 18800 Score: 21 Matches: 2(2) Sequen
Leptin OS=Homo sapiens GN=LEP PE=1 SV=1
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr(expt)	Mr(calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
1392	436.7490	871.4834	871.4763	8.11	2	(20)	0.01	1	U	L.ENLRDLL.
1395	436.7492	871.4839	871.4763	8.68	2	21	0.0086	1	U	L.ENLRDLL.

18. [1::sp|cRAP086|P01012|OVAL CHICK](#) Mass: 43196 Score: 21 Matches: 1(1) Sequen
Ovalbumin OS=Gallus gallus GN=SERPINB14 PE=1 SV=2
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr(expt)	Mr(calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
4373	552.7748	1103.5351	1103.5094	23.3	0	21	0.0085	1	U	F.QTAADQ

19. [1::sp|cRAP114|O00762|UBE2C HUMAN](#) Mass: 19754 Score: 20 Matches: 1(1) Sequen
Ubiquitin-conjugating enzyme E2 C OS=Homo sapiens GN=UBE2C PE=1 SV=1
Check to include this hit in error tolerant search or archive report

Query	Observed	Mr(expt)	Mr(calc)	ppm	Miss	Score	Expect	Rank	Unique	Peptide
889	415.2612	828.5078	828.5069	1.15	1	20	0.0092	1	U	Y.DVRTILL.

Search Parameters

Type of search : MS/MS Ion Search
Enzyme : Chymotrypsin
Fixed modifications : [Carbamidomethyl \(C\)](#)
Variable modifications : [Deamidated \(NQ\)](#), [DTSSP Cross link \(K\)](#), [DTSSP Cross link di oxidation \(K\)](#), [DTSSP Cross link single oxidation \(K\)](#), [DTSSP Cross link tri oxidation \(K\)](#), [Oxidation \(M\)](#)
Mass values : Monoisotopic
Protein Mass : Unrestricted
Peptide Mass Tolerance : $\pm$ 25 ppm
Fragment Mass Tolerance: $\pm$ 0.8 Da
Max Missed Cleavages : 2
Instrument type : ESI-TRAP
Number of queries : 11798

Mascot: <http://www.matrixscience.com/>